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Social Intelligence And Test Anxiety As Psychological Correlates Of Academic Achievement Among Public Senior Secondary School Students In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

Academic achievement is a crucial outcome for secondary school students, influenced by a range of cognitive, emotional, and behavioral factors. This study examined social intelligence and test anxiety as psychological correlates of academic achievement among public senior secondary school students in Anambra State, Nigeria. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. A correlational research design was adopted. The population comprised of 20,560 senior secondary school students (SSS II) in the 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State, from which a sample of 392 students were selected using stratified random sampling techniques. Three instruments were collected using standardized instruments: Social Intelligence Scale Questionnaire (SIS), Test Anxiety Inventory Questionnaire (TAI). The reliability of these instruments were established to be 0.83, and 0.80 respectively; and the third instrument was students' academic achievement scores obtained from examination scores of teacher-made tests obtained from PPSSC portal Awka, 2023/2024. Data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and multiple regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance. The results revealed a significant positive relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement, while test anxiety showed a significant negative relationship with academic achievement. Furthermore, social intelligence and test anxiety jointly predicted academic achievement. The study concluded that psychological variables play a crucial role in students' academic success and recommended the integration of social skills development and anxiety management strategies into school counselling programmes.

Keywords: Social intelligence; test anxiety; psychological, academic achievement.

INTRODUCTION

Education has manifold functions in man's modern society. It is for preservation, transformation, transfer and advancement of knowledge and it is also devoted to bringing changes for the good of the society. The importance of education lies in the fact that it is considered as a key for bolstering human resource for sustainable economic and social change. This is in line with the Nigerian vision 2020 which recognized education and training within the social pillar, as one of the platforms that will transform Nigeria into a large, strong, diversified, sustainable and competitive economy that effectively harnesses the talents and energies of its people and responsibly exploits its natural endowments to guarantee a high standard of living and quality of life for its citizens.

In the field of education, student's educational outcomes and achievement are evaluated and graded using examinations and tests. Academic achievement is a direct manifestation of learning effectiveness and a valid indicator to evaluate the effectiveness of teaching and education in higher institution as well as the overall development of students. Academic achievement of students is influenced by various factors, and researchers have done a lot of research to examine the factors in a bid to addressing the problem and leveraging secondary school students performance. Studies have shown that academic achievement is related with good relationship, communication skills, self-awareness; self-regulation, study skill; goal setting, and time management which are elements of social intelligence, and test anxiety. These underscored the need for effective teaching strategies and quality of instruction by teachers at the secondary level of education. Academic achievement remains a central goal of secondary education and a major indicator of students' success within the educational system. In many developing countries, including Nigeria, students' academic performance in internal and external examinations determines access to higher education and future career opportunities. Although cognitive ability has traditionally been emphasized, contemporary research increasingly recognizes the importance of psychological and emotional factors in shaping academic outcomes (Putwain & Daly, 2021; Aremu & Sokan, 2022).

Social intelligence refers to the ability to understand social situations, manage interpersonal relationships, and interact effectively with others. Students with high levels of social intelligence are more likely to communicate effectively, collaborate with peers, and develop positive relationships with teachers, which may enhance learning and academic achievement (Khodabakhsh & Mansouri, 2021; Adeyemo, 2023). In the context of this study, social intelligence is an overall self- and social-consciousness estimate, evolved social perceptions and opinions, and readiness and desire to manage complex change in society. Socially intelligent students are more likely to be active, especially concerning their academic work and other school activities. Test anxiety has been suggested as one of the factors that could influence academic achievement.

Test anxiety, on the other hand, is a psychological condition characterized by excessive worry, tension, and emotional arousal during examination situations. High levels of test anxiety have been linked to impaired concentration, poor memory retrieval, and reduced academic performance among secondary school students (Putwain et al., 2022; Onyeizugbo & Nwankwo, 2024). In examination-oriented school systems, test anxiety remains a significant threat to students' academic success. Test is a very important phenomena in schooling. Students are expected to take several tests in the course of their schooling. These tests are used to evaluate the students' progress throughout their course of study (as continuous assessment). Educators and policy makers use examination record to assess the effectiveness of their instruction and identify ways to improve it, (Olatan & Moroluyo, 2014). Testing is common in everyday life as students have to take many highly competitive centralized and high stakes examination such as the Common Entrance Examination (C.E.E.), First School Leaving Certificate Examination (F.S.L.C.E.), Junior Secondary School Certificate Examination (J.S.C.E), Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (S.S.C.E.), Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME), Post-UTME, and a host of others. These series of examinations play a considerable pressure on the students. Possibly due to pressure to perform well, among other factors, students often experience heightened stress and anxiety during the examination (Ibeawuchi & Iruloh, 2017).

Majority of research works done on the effects of social intelligence and test anxiety on students' academic achievement mainly indicated a positive relationship between social intelligence and achievement and a negative relationship between test anxiety and achievement (Chapell, Blanding, Silverstein, Takahashi, Newman, Gubi & McCann, 2005; Stober, 2004). However, the research findings in the studies carried out by some researchers are thus, Obilor and Ikpa (2020), investigated social intelligence and academic achievement of senior secondary school students. The correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was 800 respondents, while 30% of the population was used to obtain a sample size of 240 senior secondary school students. The simple random sampling technique was adopted for the study. A structured questionnaire titled "Social Intelligence and Academic Achievement" (SIAAA) with a four point rating scale was designed, and a reliability

coefficient of 0.81 was obtained using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation. Mean was used to answer the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation analysis. It was found that significant relationship exist between self-awareness and academic achievement of students; self-motivation and academic achievement of students; and empathy and academic achievement of students. The study is related to the present study because both are concerned with the relationship of social intelligence and academic achievement of students. Though the population and sample size differ from the present study. Adewale, (2021), examined the link between social intelligence and academic achievement among senior secondary students in Lagos State. A correlational survey of 300 students revealed a significant positive relationship between social intelligence and students' grade point averages. The study recommends integrating social intelligence training into school programs to boost performance. The study is related to the present study because both are concerned with the relationship of social intelligence and academic achievement. Both were done in Nigeria.

Ibrahim, (2020), investigated how social intelligence contributes to students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Kano State. Using standardized scales, data from 250 students showed that students with higher social intelligence scored better in group projects and final exams. The study advocates for group-based learning activities to develop students' social skills. The study is related to the present study because both are concerned with the relationship of social intelligence and academic achievement. The study and the present effort were done in Nigeria. Aliyu, (2021), investigated the impact of test anxiety on the academic performance of senior secondary school students in Kaduna State. A sample of 250 students was selected through stratified random sampling. The findings revealed that high test anxiety significantly lowered students' scores across subjects. The study recommends implementing test anxiety management workshops in schools. The study is related to the present study because they both focused on academic achievement and test anxiety. However, they differ, for while the study under review was done in Kaduna State the present study was in Anambra State of Nigeria. Despite growing interest in psychological correlates of academic achievement, limited empirical studies have jointly examined social intelligence and test anxiety among public senior secondary school students. This study therefore seeks to address this gap.

Statement of the Problem

In the contemporary educational landscape, academic achievement is a critical indicator of student success and future opportunities. The success or failure of students in both internal and external examinations have attracted the attention of stakeholders in the education sector. The falling performance in both internal and external examination as reported by teachers and some officials of state ministry of education in Anambra state has been a source of concern to parents, teachers, school administrators, educational planners, psychologists, guidance counselors, stakeholders and the government. This is more distressing when one reflects on the amount of resources the government invest in the education sector annually. The poor performance of students in school test and examination have instigated researchers among scholars to find redress to the ugly development. Some of such studies were carried out by researchers at the primary and post-secondary levels. Most of these studies attributed the declining rate to certain psychological attributes like, locus of control, self-esteem, self-efficacy and sometimes lack of interest by students. However, there seem to be no much evidence of empirical studies conducted at the post-primary school level which hinged on certain attributes, such as social intelligence, and test anxiety. It is this gap that the present study intends to fill. The problem of this study is stated thus: What are the psychological relationship among social intelligence, test anxiety, and academic achievement of senior secondary two (SS11) students in public secondary school in Anambra State.

Purpose and Scope of the Study

The major purpose of this study is to investigate social intelligence and test anxiety as psychological correlates of academic achievement among public senior secondary school students. This study is specifically designed to determine: (a) The relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement of senior secondary two (SS11) students in public secondary schools. (b) The relationship

between test anxiety and academic achievement of public senior secondary two (SS11) students in public secondary schools. (c) The joint relationship among social intelligence, test anxiety, and academic achievement of senior secondary two (SS11) students in public secondary schools. The study is delimited to investigation of social intelligence and test anxiety as psychological correlates of academic achievement among public senior secondary school students in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study: (1) What is the relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement among public senior secondary school students? (2) What is the relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement among public senior secondary school students? (3) To what extent do social intelligence and test anxiety jointly predict academic achievement among public senior secondary school students?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses formulated guided the study and were tested at 0.05 significance levels. (1) There is no significant relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement among public senior secondary school students. (2) There is no significant relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement among public senior secondary school students. (3) Social intelligence and test anxiety do not significantly predict academic achievement among public senior secondary school students.

RESEARCH METHODS

Design of the Study The study is a correlational survey. Correlation survey research aimed at establishing relationships among two or more variables without any attempt to influence them. Correlational research is used to describe the relationship between two or more naturally occurring variables (Nworgu, 2016).

Population of the Study The population of the study consists of 20,560 senior secondary school students (SS II) in the 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State (PPSC, 2024). These SS II students are in the six education zones in the state.

Sample and Sampling Techniques The sample of the study comprised 392 SS11 students drawn from the population using Taro-Yamane. The sample size represented approximately **1.91%** of the total population. Stratified random sampling technique was used to select three schools from each Education Zone for good representation, making a total of 18 schools.

Instrument for Data Collection

Three instruments were used to collect data for the study. The instruments include: Social Intelligence Scale Questionnaire (SIS) designed by Donald G. F. (1983), Test Anxiety Inventory Questionnaire (TAI) designed by Charles D. Spielberger. (1980), and Achievement Test Scores (ATS) obtained from examination scores of teachers made tests in Mathematics and English from PPSSC portal Awka, 2023/2024. Two of the instruments were non-cognitive assessment tools, while one is cognitive assessment tool (Teacher-made test scores/exam scores). The questionnaire consisted of two parts, section A and B. Section A was used to collect demographic information, that is, Bio Data of the respondents. Section B consists of the item statements, divided into three parts. Specifically, the first part contains 21 items on social intelligence, and the second part contains 17 items on test anxiety. This section was arranged on a four-point scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD).

Validation and Reliability of the Instrument

The instruments used were standardized. The instruments were trial-tested. The responses of the respondents were collated to ascertain the internal consistency of the items in each of the instruments. Cronbach Alpha Method was used. The computation yielded co-efficient values of 0.83, and 0.80, for Social Intelligence Questionnaire, and Test Anxiety Questionnaire.

Method of Data Collection

The researcher administered the questionnaire directly to the respondents with the help of six research assistants who are teachers in the sampled public schools visited. On the spot method was adopted

because it facilitated retrieval of the instrument and motivated the respondents. The questionnaires were numbered and tagged in line with the arrangement of the students' names in the terminal result sheets to ensure that the numbering followed how the students were given the questionnaire to answer. This was to ensure that appropriate achievement scores of the students are properly tagged with their responses on the questionnaire. At the end of the exercise, out of the 392 questionnaires administered, 386 were retrieved, which was 98.9 percentage rate of retrieval.

Method of Data Analysis

the data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and multiple regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement among senior secondary school (SSII) students in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Pearson r Analysis showing the relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement among senior secondary (SSII) school students in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Source of Variation		Social Intelligence r	Academic Achievement r	Remarks
Social Intelligence	Pearson Correlation	1	0.679	High positive relationship
	N	386	386	
Academic Achievement	Pearson Correlation	0.679	1	
	N	386	386	

The result presented in Table 1 revealed Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.679$). This indicated a high positive relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement among Senior Secondary (SSII) students in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Pearson r showing the relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement among Senior Secondary (SSII) students in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Source Of Variation		Test Anxiety r	Academic Achievement r	Remark
Test Anxiety	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.313	Moderate negative relationship
	N	386	386	
Academic Achievement	Pearson Correlation	-0.313	1	
	N	386	386	

Table 2 showed that the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was -0.313 . This indicated a moderate negative relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement. The negative correlation implies that as test anxiety increases, academic achievement slightly decreases, although the relationship was moderate.

Research Question 3: *What is the combined relationship among social intelligence, test anxiety, and academic achievement among Senior Secondary Two (SSII) students in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 3: Summary regression Analysis on the joint relationship among social intelligence, test anxiety, academic engagement, and academic achievement among Senior Secondary Two (SSII) students in public secondary schools.

N	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	R Square Change	% added	Remark
386	0.719	0.517	0.513	0.517	51.3	High correlation

Table 3 examines the combined relationship among social intelligence, test anxiety, and academic achievement among Senior Secondary Two (SSII) students in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The results indicate the multiple correlation coefficient (R) = 0.719, suggesting a high positive relationship among the independent variables (social intelligence, and test anxiety,) and the dependent variable (academic achievement). The Adjusted R² = 0.513, indicates that after adjusting for potential overestimation, the independent variables still account for 51.3% of the variance in academic achievement.

Null Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement among Senior Secondary Two (SSII) students in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Pearson r Test of significance of relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement among senior secondary school students in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Source Of Variation		Social Intelligence	Academic Achievement	Remarks
Social Intelligence	Pearson Correlation	1	0.679*	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	
	N	386	386	
Academic Achievement	Pearson Correlation	0.679	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		
	N	386	386	

Table 4 showed that the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) = 0.679, with a p-value of 0.000 (p < 0.05). This indicated a strong positive relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement. Since the p-value (0.000) is less than the 0.05 significance level, the null hypothesis, which stated that there was no significant relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement is rejected. There was a significant relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement among Senior Secondary Two (SSII) students in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Null Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement among Senior Secondary (SSII) students in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 5: Pearson r Test of significance of relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement among Senior Secondary (SSII) students in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Source Of Variation		Test Anxiety r	Academic Achievement r	Remarks0
Test Anxiety	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.313	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	
	N	386	386	
Academic Achievement	Pearson Correlation	-0.313**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		
	N	386	386	

The Table 5 showed that the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) = -0.313, with a p-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). Since the p-value (0.000) is less than the 0.05 significance level, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement was rejected. This indicated that test anxiety has a significant negative relationship with academic achievement among SSII students in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Null Hypothesis 3: There is no significant joint relationship among social intelligence, test anxiety, and academic achievement among Senior Secondary Two (SSII) students in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 6: Summary of regression analysis on the joint relationship among social intelligence, test anxiety, and academic achievement among Senior Secondary Two (SSII) students in public secondary schools.

N	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	R Square Change	% added	df	F-cal	p-value	Remark
386	0.719	0.517	0.513	0.517	51.3	382	136.182	0.000	Significant

Findings in Table 6 revealed that at 382 df denominator, the F-calculated value is 136.182, with a p-value of 0.000, which is statistically significant at 0.05 level. Since the p-value is less than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance, the stated null hypothesis is rejected, there is a significant joint relationship among social intelligence, test anxiety, and academic achievement among Senior Secondary Two (SSII) students in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Summary of Major Findings Findings presented in the tables are summarized as follows: (a) There is a high positive relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement ($r = 0.679$). (b) There is a moderate negative relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement ($r = -0.313$). (c) There is a high positive relationship among the independent variables (social intelligence, and test anxiety,) and the dependent variable (academic achievement) ($\text{Adjusted } R^2 = 0.513$). (d) There is a significant relationship between social intelligence and academic achievement among Senior Secondary Two (SSII) students in public secondary schools in Anambra State. (e) Test anxiety has a significant negative relationship with academic achievement among SSII students in public secondary schools in Anambra State. (f) There is a significant joint relationship among social intelligence, test anxiety, and academic achievement among Senior Secondary Two (SSII) students in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding that social intelligence is positively related to academic achievement supports recent empirical studies emphasizing the role of interpersonal competence in academic success (Adeyemo, 2023; Khodabakhsh & Mansouri, 2021). Socially intelligent students are better able to engage in cooperative learning, seek academic assistance, and maintain productive relationships within the school environment. The significant negative relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement aligns with contemporary research indicating that excessive anxiety disrupts cognitive processing during examinations (Putwain & Daly, 2021; Onyeizugbo & Nwankwo, 2024). These findings underscore the importance of addressing emotional factors in secondary school education.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that social intelligence and test anxiety are significant psychological correlates of academic achievement among public senior secondary school students. Interventions aimed at enhancing social intelligence and reducing test anxiety are likely to improve students' academic performance

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made: (1) School counsellors should design programmes that enhance students' social intelligence and interpersonal skills. (2) Test anxiety management strategies, including relaxation techniques and examination preparation skills, should be integrated into school counselling services. (3) Teachers should create supportive classroom

environments that reduce examination-related stress. (4) Educational policymakers should incorporate psychological support services into secondary school education programmes

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